

Analysis of Wireless Measurements and Sensor Data for Autonomous Mobility in Industrial Environments

Bachelorabschlussarbeit

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Eidesstattliche Erklärung

Hiermit erkläre ich, dass ich die vorliegende Arbeit selbstständig und eigenhändig sowie ohne unerlaubte fremde Hilfe und ausschließlich unter Verwendung der aufgeführten Quellen und Hilfsmittel angefertigt habe.

Berlin, den 09.12.2022

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Abstract

The following thesis contains an analysis of data from the Enway Campaign which was conducted in 2021 and offered as a bachelor's thesis by Fraunhofer HHI.

The Enway Campaign is part of the AI4Mobile research project that is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research under the umbrella of the Artificial Intelligence in Communication Networks plan within the scope of the German Federal Government's High-Tech Strategy. The project intends to develop methodologies that provide sustainable Quality of Service (QoS) prediction at high mobility by combining data from the entire mobile network with secondary data from vehicles, applications, or the environment. The result of this campaign which is in the form of several sets of wireless measurement and sensor data will be utilized for machine learning activities. In addition to that, the sensor data will be processed to create a clearance model that acts as the target prediction of the machine learning classifier.

This thesis deals with analyzing sensor data to derive Line-of-Sight (LoS) prediction from the clearance model using the Fresnel Zone Clearance Model and also create a classifier for LoS prediction using machine learning classifiers such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, and Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB) from the wireless measurement.

Zusammenfassung

Die folgende Arbeit handelt es sich um eine Analyse von Daten der Enway-Kampagne, die im Jahr 2021 durchgeführt und als Bachelorarbeit vom Fraunhofer HHI angeboten wurde.

Die Enway-Kampagne ist Teil des Forschungsprojekts AI4Mobile, das vom Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung (BMBF) unter dem Dach des Plans Künstliche Intelligenz in Kommunikationsnetzen im Rahmen der Hightech-Strategie der Bundesregierung gefördert wird. Das Projekt beabsichtigt, Methoden zu entwickeln, die eine nachhaltige QoS Vorhersage bei hoher Mobilität ermöglichen, indem Daten aus dem gesamten Mobilfunknetz mit Sekundärdaten aus Fahrzeugen, Anwendungen oder der Umgebung kombiniert werden. Das Ergebnis dieser Kampagne in Form mehrerer drahtloser Mess- und Sensordatensätze wird für maschinelle Lernaktivitäten verwendet. Darüber hinaus werden die Sensordaten verarbeitet, um ein Freiraummodell zu erstellen, das als Zielvorhersage des maschinell lernenden Klassifikators dient.

Diese Bachelorarbeit befasst sich mit der Analyse von Sensordaten zur Ableitung der Sichtlinienvorhersage (LoS) aus dem Freiraummodell unter Verwendung des Fresnel Zonen Freiraummodells und der Erstellung eines Klassifikators für die Sichtlinienvorhersage (LoS) unter Verwendung von maschinell lernenden Klassifikatoren wie Decision Tree, Random Forest und XGB aus der drahtlosen Messung.

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AT	Attention
AUC	Area Under ROC Curve
BMBF	Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung
BS	Base Station
EPC	Evolved Packet Core
LiDAR	Light Detection and Ranging
LoS	Line-of-Sight
LTE	Long Term Evolution
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
nLoS	non-Line-of-Sight
PHY	Physical
QoS	Quality of Service
ROC	Receiver Operating Characteristic
RSRP	Reference Signal Received Power
RSRQ	Reference Signal Received Quality
RSSI	Received Signal Strength Indication
SINR	Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio
SLAM	Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
TDD	Time-Division Duplexing
UE	User Equipment
XGB	Extreme Gradient Boosting

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1 Introduction

An Automated Guided Vehicle (AGV) is a mobile robot that is often used in factories, warehouses, and inventories across several industries. They serve as a distribution system for the processing and transfer of various commodities. These vehicles automate the workplace, reducing the amount of time and work needed [Kar+16]. Nearly all manufacturing facilities operate AGV, along with businesses in paper & printing, food & beverage, and other sectors [Cha+19].

Additionally, the data that are used in this work are collected from an AGV in the form of an autonomous sweeper from Enway [Gar+22]. While the AGV drives through a dedicated path, the AGV also collected data from its sensor and wireless measurement between the AGV and the base station. Furthermore, in many use cases of AGV in industrial environments, data that are captured by the AGV can be used to predict the QoS. For instance, the cooperation between AGVs and stationary robots where the main purpose is to have a stationary robot load and unload products to an AGV without the AGV having to stop [Kul+21]. To synchronize the load handling and identify the location of the AGV, additional sensors, such as camera systems, are currently used. With the data provided by the AGV, synchronization of the load handling could be achieved by providing the prediction of QoS which portrays how reliable the communication link will be. As a result, it is possible to avoid using extra specialized sensors, such as cameras and image analysis at the stationary robot, potentially cutting costs. The prediction of QoS is also beneficial for use cases such as *Traffic Management and Velocity Adaptation* for AGV in factory building where the main idea of this case is to maintain the traffic between several AGVs [Kul+21]. Information, namely link stability, anticipatory velocity, and route adaptation, is available through the prediction of QoS ensuring the central entity to identifies the best decision for the AGV and achieves higher efficiency. Furthermore, it enables more AGVs to operate simultaneously, which speeds up the transfer of products.

The focus of this thesis is to analyze the potential of data collected by AGV as an enabler of Artificial Intelligence (AI) for telecommunication in industrial environments. The data from the AGV will be utilized to predict LoS between the AGV and the base station. First, the sensor data are analyzed to derive LoS using the Fresnel Zone Clearance Model. A few features from the sensor data that are collected from the AGV are the position of the sweeper as given by odometry techniques and a static map. Fundamentally, a Fresnel Zone Clearance Model is created between the odometry path and the base station. Then, the total of the obstacles inside the Fresnel Zone is calculated and the values in the area of transition between LoS and nLoS are examined. The value in the area of transition will become the threshold to determine LoS. When the area of LoS is discovered, prediction of LoS using wireless measurement features such as Reference Signal Received Power (RSRP), Reference Signal Received Quality (RSRQ), Received Signal Strength Indication (RSSI), and Signal-to-Interference-plus-Noise Ratio (SINR) gathered by the AGV will be analyzed. The prediction of LoS is achieved by creating a Machine Learning (ML) classifier such as a Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGB with wireless measurement from the AGV as its input.

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2.1 Clearance Model

In an industrial environment, the path that the AGV drives through is predetermined. However, the environment between AGV and the base station might change due to obstacles and could potentially cause a disturbance in the communication channel. To analyze the disturbance, path clearance between AGV and base station is evaluated commonly by applying the Fresnel Zone Clearance Model. The assessment of how much of the Fresnel Zone is obscured by obstacles could be used to determine the availability of LoS [JHJ15].

A Fresnel Zone is a buffer that is structured resembling a prolate spheroid (an ellipse that is "pointy" instead of "squashed") around the LoS that separates two objects, as seen in Figure 2.1. Based on the distance from the objects and the transmission frequency, its radius varies. It increases in size as one moves away from the center point, which is the point that is equally far from both objects [Bro+20].

Figure 2.1: Fresnel Zone [Jcm12]

A Fresnel Zone is made up of multiple layers or zones depending on its radius, especially the semi-minor axis represented as b in Figure 2.1. The first zone, which is the zone with the smallest semi-minor axis, must be kept mostly clear of obstacles to prevent interfering with the radio reception. However, a minor Fresnel Zone interference is often acceptable. When 80% of the corresponding first Fresnel Zone is unobstructed, the wireless connection is said to be free space [JHJ15].

Figure 2.2 shows the parameter of an ellipse with a and b representing semi-major and semi-minor axis, respectively. The point F_1 and F_2 represent the AGV and Base Station where D as presented in Figure 2.1 is the distance between them. To create the Fresnel Zone, the semi-minor axis of the Fresnel Zone should first be calculated.

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Figure 2.2: Ellipse [Ag217]

The formula to calculate the semi-minor axis is as follows:

$$b_n = \frac{1}{2} \sqrt{n\lambda D} \quad \text{with} \quad \lambda = \frac{c}{f} \quad (2.1)$$

In Equation (2.1), n is the indexing of the n -th Fresnel Zone, c is the speed of light, and f is the carrier frequency. The semi-major axis a could be calculated with the Pythagoras theorem. Once the semi-minor and semi-major of the Fresnel Zone are found, the ellipse could be constructed. Since the ellipse is not always in a horizontal or vertical form and can be formed at an angle, the formula for a general ellipse should be altered. The formula of the first Fresnel Zone with $n = 1$ and $b_1 = b$ is as follows:

$$\frac{x^2}{a^2} + \frac{y^2}{b^2} \leq 1 \quad (2.2)$$

With the help of the polar coordinate system, x and y are given as follows:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \rho \cos(\varphi) \\ \rho \sin(\varphi) \end{pmatrix}; \quad \varphi = [0, 2\pi[\quad (2.3)$$

since ρ is already defined for the x and y axis as a and b , the polar coordinate is assigned as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a \cos(\varphi) \\ b \sin(\varphi) \end{pmatrix}; \quad \varphi = [0, 2\pi[\quad (2.4)$$

Rotate the ellipse with rotation matrix R and substitute x and y from Equation (2.4):

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = R \begin{pmatrix} a \cos(\varphi) \\ b \sin(\varphi) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.5)$$

$$\begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & -\sin(\theta) \\ \sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} a \cos(\varphi) \\ b \sin(\varphi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.6)$$

Multiply both sides with inverse rotation matrix $R^{-1} = R^T$:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \cos(\theta) & \sin(\theta) \\ -\sin(\theta) & \cos(\theta) \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} x \\ y \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} a \cos(\varphi) \\ b \sin(\varphi) \end{pmatrix} \quad (2.7)$$

With matrix multiplication, the following equations are given:

$$x \cos(\theta) + y \sin(\theta) = a \cos(\varphi) \quad (2.8)$$

$$y \cos(\theta) - x \sin(\theta) = b \sin(\varphi) \quad (2.9)$$

Translate the center of the ellipse from $(0,0)$ to (x_c, y_c) and isolate $\cos(\varphi)$ and $\sin(\varphi)$:

$$\frac{(x - x_c) \cos(\theta) + (y - y_c) \sin(\theta)}{a} = \cos(\varphi) \quad (2.10)$$

$$\frac{(y - y_c) \cos(\theta) - (x - x_c) \sin(\theta)}{b} = \sin(\varphi) \quad (2.11)$$

With the help of Pythagorean trigonometric identity (2.12) and substitution of both the Equations (2.10) and (2.11), the Equation (2.13) as the formula for the Fresnel Zone ellipse is given:

$$\cos^2(\varphi) + \sin^2(\varphi) = 1 \quad (2.12)$$

$$\left[\frac{(x - x_c) \cos(\theta) + (y - y_c) \sin(\theta)}{a} \right]^2 + \left[\frac{(y - y_c) \cos(\theta) - (x - x_c) \sin(\theta)}{b} \right]^2 \leq 1 \quad (2.13)$$

In Equation (2.13), θ represents the angle of rotation counterclockwise and the symbol \leq is used to also account for points inside the ellipse.

2.2 Data Prediction/Classification

Machine Learning (ML) is a major element of AI that allows it to learn and improve on its own. Identifying patterns in targeted data, creating descriptive models, and predicting objects even without having clear predefined rules and models are a few abilities of the ML algorithm [Mam+18]. ML has been used in many sectors such as in the medical sector where ML is used to predict whether a person has breast cancer [BD22]. Another example would be in the educational environment where ML helps identify Student Attentiveness [Ros+13]. In addition, ML also contributes to the industrial environment to predict QoS as mentioned in Section 1.

ML algorithms are broadly categorized into four paradigms [Mam+18]:

- **Supervised learning:** A function to predict output values is produced by this learning algorithm. First, an established training data set is analyzed to begin the procedure. Using labels and new data, this algorithm could be used to predict future occurrences from previously learned data.

2 Theoretical Background

- Unsupervised learning: This algorithm identifies data that has not been categorized or labeled in a training data set. Additionally, it performs studies to deduce a function from a system to explain a concealed structure from unlabeled data. The method of unsupervised learning is clustering.
- Semi-supervised learning: It incorporates features from both supervised and unsupervised learning. These algorithms take a huge amount of unlabeled data and a small amount of labeled data.
- Reinforcement: This algorithm involves interacting with the environment through actions and error discovery. It enables software agents and machines to decide what behavior is appropriate in each situation to maximize performance.

One of the many features of ML is the ability to classify data or make a prediction to match a certain category which falls into the supervised learning of ML. In classification, assessments are made based on values acquired during observation. This method uses a mapping function, say f , on input variables, say x , to approximate a discrete output variable, say y . Although classification output is often discrete, it may alternatively be continuous for each class label in the form of probability [Mam+18]. For this work, the ML models will be taken from the Python package *Scikit-learn* [Ped+11], an open-source library including coding for various ML tasks such as regression, classification, and clustering [Ma21]. The classification algorithm that will be assessed for this work is Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGB.

2.2.1 Decision Tree

One of the most important components of inductive learning is Decision Tree Induction. It is among the most popular and useful techniques for the inductive approach. Using a training set as a starting point, the following is a general process for creating a Decision Tree and is visualized in Figure 2.3. The root node of the tree is first thought of as the complete training set. The root node is then divided into several sub-nodes using certain heuristic data. If a sub-node contains instances that are members of a specific class, it is referred to be a leaf node, otherwise, it will keep splitting the sub-node based on the heuristic data. Up until all leaf nodes are produced, this procedure is repeated [Li+09]. Figure 2.3 illustrates a Decision Tree for street crossing as an example.

Figure 2.3: Decision Tree [Pro]

2.2.2 Random Forest

Random Forest is a classification technique implementing supervised ML that combines different Decision Trees. Due to its increased performance using the ensemble approach of aggregating multiple trees and choosing the best result from a varied group of predictors, the Random Forest is preferred over a single Decision Tree. Random Forest training is based on the bootstrap approach, where each Decision Tree learns from random samples of the data set during training, and these samples are utilized repeatedly (as a replacement) for the Decision Tree. Then, Random Forest selects a random subset of features from the data set and generates a collection of Decision Trees with the previously selected random samples. The final class of the input is then determined by averaging the prediction results from these Decision Trees. The process is visualized in Figure 2.4. This algorithm works effectively because a single Decision Tree is sensitive to noise, but several Decision Trees reduce the noise and provide more accurate predictions [Tam20].

2.2.3 Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGB)

Gradient boosting refers to a class of ensemble ML algorithms that could be applied for regression and classification models. To create ensembles, Decision Tree models are used. Trees are introduced to the ensembles one at a time, and their purpose is to mitigate the prediction mistakes generated by the prior models. The gradient boosting method has an effective open-source implementation called XGB. XGB helps researchers to solve large-scale problems in the real world by using a smaller number of resources [Sar+21].

Figure 2.4: Random Forest [unk]

Figure 2.5: XGB [WCC20]

3 Data Source

The following section is taken from an AI4Mobile research project report "Final description of the collected data" on how the measurement of data by the autonomous sweeper AGV is conducted [Gar+22]. It should be noted that the report is not publicly available and this thesis will not focus on how the data is collected.

An autonomous sweeper from Enway with an attached User Equipment (UE) linked to a private Long Term Evolution (LTE) network with a single base station was utilized to perform a measurement campaign at the Enway facilities in Berlin (see Figure 3.1). The autonomous sweeper traced the same track (see Figure 3.2) several times, sweeping the inside of the building and a small portion of the outside. The base station for this campaign was placed inside and attenuators were employed to offer a variety of radio measurements, including connection losses. The only network-connected device was the UE, and traffic between the UE and a local server was generated and recorded on both the UE and server sides. More than 40000 seconds of measurements are collected in the data.

Figure 3.1: Autonomous Cleaning Sweeper Provided by Enway [Gar+22]

Figure 3.2: Route (black) of sweeper for several rounds of measurements including indoor (green) and outdoor (blue). The position of the base station provided by Götting (right picture) is marked by the yellow cross [Gar+22].

The radio and system characteristics of the LTE network are as follows:

- EPC: 4G Core acc. 3GPP Rel. 15
- BS: 3GPP Rel. 9
- TDD system with 20 MHz bandwidth

3 Data Source

- Frequency at 3790 MHz in the industrial spectrum between 3.7GHz and 3.8GHz
- Output power: 24 dBm, 2x2 MIMO
- Radiation pattern of build-in antennas: opening angle hor. 60°, vert. 60°
- Gain: 6 dBi
- Size (H x W x D): 330 x 230 x 130

A variety of sensors on the autonomous sweeper were used to collect data throughout the campaign. Included are the following attributes:

- Position of the sweeper as given by odometry techniques.
- Light Detection and Ranging (LiDAR) data: A point-cloud of reflected obstacles such as walls and standing objects, identified with x,y, and z coordinates.
- Static elevation map: A precomputed, static occupancy grid.
- Far and near map obstacles: Occupancy grids that are relative to the sweeper's position and created dynamically in real-time. See Figure 3.3 for details.

Figure 3.3: Dynamic Obstacle Maps [Gar+22]

Through the use of proprietary algorithms for sensor fusion and Simultaneous Localization and Mapping (SLAM), the occupancy grids are produced from the raw sensor data. Along with the sensor data, the following features were captured:

- Full UE LTE Stack was captured (MobileInsight [Li+16])
- Physical (PHY) Layer Measurements: RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, and SINR are also available via Attention (AT)-command-based measurements
- QoS Measurements (e.g., Throughput and round-trip time from ping command)

The full data set from this autonomous sweeper measurement campaign has been published in [Her+22].

4 Evaluation Methodology

It should be mentioned that for this work, the data that will be used is not the full data set that the AGV gathered as mentioned in Section 3 and only the data that is relevant for LoS prediction is analyzed. The relevant data are sensor data that is collected in the form of *.bag* files, PHY Layer Measurements such as RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, and SINR in a form of *.log* files, and the Full UE LTE Stack from MobileInsight [Li+16] in a form of *.mi2log* files. First, the focus will be pointed at the sensor data by extracting the *.bag* files to give out the appropriate features.

4.1 Sensor Data

The *.bag* files contain different types of messages that store information of the measurement. The following Table 4.1 shows several types of messages.

Table 4.1: Topic Table from the *.bag* File

Topics	Types	Message Count	Frequency
<i>/drive_state</i>	<i>simple_drive_msgs/SimpleDrive</i>	29508	49.997664
<i>/global_odom</i>	<i>nav_msgs/Odometry</i>	17705	30.001102
<i>/navigation/enway_map/far_map_obstacles</i>	<i>nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid</i>	11753	20.051698
<i>/navigation/enway_map/map_static_elevation</i>	<i>nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid</i>	1	NaN
<i>/navigation/enway_map/near_map_obstacles</i>	<i>nav_msgs/OccupancyGrid</i>	11753	20.015242
<i>/sensors/inertial/imu</i>	<i>sensor_msgs/Imu</i>	58944	98.474022
<i>/sensors/lidar/lidar_top/points</i>	<i>sensor_msgs/PointCloud2</i>	5902	10.000963
<i>/tf</i>	<i>tf2_msgs/TFMessage</i>	94738	148.971906
<i>/tf_static</i>	<i>tf2_msgs/TFMessage</i>	2	950.658205

Two topics are important for this thesis, namely */global_odom* and */navigation/enway_map/map_static_elevation*. The topic */global_odom* contains the odometry position of the AGV while the topic */navigation/enway_map/map_static_elevation* contains the layout of the static map. The data contained in both topics will play an important part in creating the Fresnel Zone which determines LoS between AGV and the base station. The workflow of this thesis will be explained further in Section 4.3.

4.2 Wireless Measurement

There are two wireless measurements from the Enway Campaign that is relevant for this work, namely the PHY Layer Measurements such as RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, and SINR via AT-command-based measurements in a form of *.log* files and the Full UE LTE Stack captured with MobileInsight [Li+16] in a form of *.mi2log* files. First, the *.mi2log* files are parsed and the features are

4 Evaluation Methodology

observed. After parsing the files, the only relevant features for this work that is contained in the files are RSRP and RSRQ. Since features such as RSSI and SINR that are contained in the *.log* files are not available, data from the *.log* files are used in the ML activities.

However, the sampling rate of the data in the *.log* files is coarser than the sampling rate in *.mi2log* files, namely 200 ms to 40 ms. For this reason, the data inside the *.log* files should be up-sampled and observed whether the up-sampled data has a sharp contrast to the data in *.mi2log* files. Figures 4.1 and 4.2 show the difference between the up-sampled data and data from the *.mi2log* files.

Figure 4.1: RSRP Comparison

Figure 4.2: RSRQ Comparison

It is clear from Figures 4.1 and 4.2 that the difference is tolerable and therefore the up-sampled data could be used for ML activities.

4.3 Workflow

The *.bag* files are first extracted using the python package *bagpy* [Bha]. From the topic */global_odom* which contains the odometry path of the AGV and the topic */navigation/enway_map/map_static_elevation* which contains the static map, the following Figure 4.3 is created.

Figure 4.3: Static Map

In Figure 4.3, represented by green is the path of the AGV. The base station, represented by blue, is located inside the building. For each point of the AGV's path, a Fresnel Zone will be created between those points and the base station. To calculate the obstacle inside the Fresnel Zone, the floor of the map is entirely removed. Therefore, the values that represented the floor are not accounted for in the calculation. Figure 4.4 shows the Fresnel Zone between one point in the path of the AGV and the base station as an example and Figure 4.5 shows a heat map with the accumulated obstacles as values on each point of the path taken by the AGV. Figures 4.4, 4.5, and also 4.6 are magnified to show the path of the AGV in more detail.

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Figure 4.4: Static Map with Fresnel Zone

Figure 4.5: Heat Map

Figure 4.5 already suggests a distinction in obstacle count between the area of LoS and nLoS. To classify the LoS and nLoS area, a threshold that determines between the two classifications is needed. Therefore, the values in the area of transition between LoS and nLoS are observed, and the value that distinguishes both areas are then set as a threshold. Figure 4.6 shows a clear contrast between LoS and nLoS areas. The area of LoS is represented with green color and the area of nLoS is represented in red.

Figure 4.6: LoS and nLoS Area

After establishing the area of LoS and nLoS from the sensor data, the next step is to create LoS prediction with the data from the wireless measurement using ML. As mentioned in Section 4.2, data from the AT-command-based measurement will be used. It is important for this step that the sampling rate for the data in the *.log* files matches the sensor data. The sensor data has a sampling rate of 30 ms while data from the wireless measurement has a sampling rate of 40 ms. Here the sensor data are down-sampled to match the wireless data.

After the sensor data are down-sampled, data sets for ML activities will be created. Two versions of the data set will be used to train the ML. Both data sets include features namely, RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, SINR, and the binary LoS and nLoS classification for the target of prediction. The difference between the two data sets is the feature distance representing the distance between AGV and the base station for each point of the path taken by the AGV. It should be noted that the data that are being used for the data sets are the collection of all data from every run of the AGV and not only from a singular run.

After the data sets are created, the prediction model that uses the data set as its input is used to determine LoS and nLoS. Classification algorithms such as Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGB are used for the prediction of LoS. Then, the accuracy of each method will be compared. To train the data set, 20% of the data are used for the validation (or test) set while the other 80% as the training set. It should be noted that the data set is not split randomly. Instead, the data set is split in order where the first 80% of the data set is allocated for the training set and the remaining 20% for the validation (or test) set.

In addition, the best hyper-parameter for each classification algorithm should be decided. For the Decision Tree, only the hyper-parameter *max_depth* is observed. As the name suggests, *max_depth* limits the growth of the Decision Tree by limiting the depth of the tree. To find the best *max_depth*, k-fold cross-validation is used. In this work, the 5-fold cross-validation is assessed where this method divides the training set into five equal sections. Then, four parts of the training set are used as a training set and the remaining portion as a test set. This also means that 80% of the training set is used for training and 20% as a test set. The hyper-parameter value that gives the highest Area Under ROC Curve (AUC) score for the test set will be used to create the final prediction model. The AUC score is used to assess the performance of the model. The higher the AUC score the better the model performs.

In the Random Forest algorithm, the hyper-parameters *max_depth* and *n_estimators* are observed. *n_estimators* sets the number of trees that are used in the algorithm. The method *GridSearchCV* is used where the method will try a list of different *max_depth* and *n_estimators* values, train the training set, and find the highest AUC score for a certain *max_depth* and *n_estimators* value. The method *GridSearchCV* that will be used in this work also applies the 5-fold cross-validation to find the best hyper-parameter value that gives the highest AUC score.

Then in XGB, the hyper-parameters *max_depth*, *n_estimators*, and *learning_rate* are observed and the same method *GridSearchCV* is applied to find the best value for each hyper-parameter. After the best hyper-parameter for each classification algorithm is decided, the final prediction model for each algorithm is created and tested using the validation (or test) set which is as mentioned before, 20% of the whole data set.

5 Prediction Result

The following section discusses the result of each classification algorithm for both the data set without distance as its feature and the data set with feature distance. First, the Decision Tree algorithm is assessed. The best *max_depth* value for the classifier that gives the highest AUC score is six for the data set that has feature distance and four for the data set without feature distance. The top section of the Decision Tree for the data set with feature distance is shown in Figure 5.1, while the Decision Tree for the data set without feature distance is shown in Figure 5.2.

Figure 5.1: Top Section of the Decision Tree with Feature Distance

Figure 5.2: Top Section of the Decision Tree without Feature Distance

5 Prediction Result

To choose the root of the Decision Tree, the feature is selected by the Decision Tree classifier using the Gini criterion to measure the quality of the split. Then, to split the node into the sub-nodes, the classifier used the best split strategy which gives out the highest Gini gained from the node to the sub-nodes. This method applies to both Decision Trees using the two different data sets. In Figures 5.1 and 5.2, the root of the Decision Tree is the feature distance and RSRP respectively. However, to ensure the importance of these features, the Python package *Scikit-learn* [Ped+11] has an attribute for its classifier called *feature_importances_* which returns the importance or the contribution of a feature for the algorithm. The feature importance of both data sets in the Decision Tree is listed as the following:

Table 5.1: Feature Importance in Decision Tree

Feature	Importance	
	Data Set with Distance	Data Set without Distance
Distance	0.943239	-
RSRP	0.053288	0.979066
RSRQ	0.002017	0.002096
RSSI	0.000147	0.013137
SINR	0.001309	0.005701

From Table 5.1, the feature distance is important in the Decision Tree for the prediction of LoS. The main reason distance is important, is because the area of LoS for this work only occurs when the AGV is at its closest to the base station as seen in Figure 4.6. The algorithm took the distance value as a major decider to predict LoS since it is already clear that the closer the AGV is to the base station, the higher the probability of LoS. The feature distance also plays a significant role in the AUC score of the validation (or test) set when trained using the Decision Tree. The AUC score for the Decision Tree with the feature distance is 0.9559, while the AUC score for the Decision Tree without the feature distance is 0.9286. The AUC score for the Decision Tree with feature distance is higher in comparison with the Decision Tree without feature distance. While the feature distance is named important for this case, it could cause an issue when applied in other environments where LoS between AGV and the base station does not only occur when the AGV is at its closest to the base station.

After assessing the performance of the Decision Tree, other algorithms namely, Random Forest and XGB will be addressed. For Random Forest, the hyper-parameters that need to be tuned are *max_depth* and *n_estimators*, while for XGB, the hyper-parameters that need to be tuned are *learning_rate*, *max_depth*, and *n_estimators*. Hyper-parameters for each algorithm and each data set are listed as the following:

- Data set with feature distance:
 - Random Forest: *max_depth* = 4 and *n_estimators* = 350
 - XGB: *learning_rate* = 0.1, *max_depth* = 2, and *n_estimators* = 400
- Data set without feature distance:
 - Random Forest: *max_depth* = 2 and *n_estimators* = 300
 - XGB: *learning_rate* = 0.1, *max_depth* = 4, and *n_estimators* = 250

Random Forest and XGB classifiers also have the attribute *feature_importances_* which returns the importance of a feature and are listed in Tables 5.2 and 5.3:

Table 5.2: Feature Importance in Random Forest

Feature	Importance	
	Data Set with Distance	Data Set without Distance
Distance	0.427069	-
RSRP	0.305767	0.505130
RSRQ	0.001387	0.000674
RSSI	0.110506	0.173494
SINR	0.155270	0.320702

Table 5.3: Feature Importance in XGB

Feature	Importance	
	Data Set with Distance	Data Set without Distance
Distance	0.390010	-
RSRP	0.306542	0.306442
RSRQ	0.038372	0.133894
RSSI	0.199047	0.207965
SINR	0.066030	0.351699

Feature distance as shown in Tables 5.2 and 5.3 are proven to be important for the prediction of LoS. The reason for this occurrence is already mentioned when comparing feature importance in the Decision Tree. For the data set without feature distance, the feature RSRP and SINR have a high value. This shows that RSRP and SINR play a significant role to predict the LoS using Random Forest and XGB.

After analyzing feature importance in both classification algorithms, The AUC score for the validation (or test) set of both data sets should be compared. The AUC score for the Random Forest with feature distance is 0.9586, while the AUC score for the Random Forest without feature distance is 0.9294. Meanwhile, the AUC score for XGB with feature distance is 0.9922, while the AUC score for XGB without feature distance is 0.9491. Figure 5.3 summarized the AUC scores for the validation (or test) sets for the different classification algorithms.

Figure 5.3: AUC Score Comparison

5 Prediction Result

Figure 5.3 shows that the AUC scores for the data set with feature distance are higher than the AUC scores for the data set without feature distance. However, even when the AUC scores are lower, each classification algorithm still gives a satisfactory performance with AUC scores of more than 0.92. Furthermore, the XGB distinctly has the best performance, while the Decision Tree and Random Forest only have a slight difference between them. Additionally, AUC scores with Random Forest and XGB could also be analyzed as the number of trees in the algorithm increase. However, since trees are created differently for each algorithm and to have a direct comparison between each algorithm, the AUC scores with Random Forest and XGB would be analyzed as the number of nodes in the algorithm increase. Figure 5.4 compares the AUC scores for Random Forest and XGB as the number of nodes increases.

Figure 5.4: AUC Scores as the Number of Nodes Increase

Figure 5.4 shows how Random Forest has a stable AUC scores as the number of nodes increases and how the AUC scores for XGB increase gradually as the number of nodes increases. This also shows, how both algorithms work to achieve their final model. As previously mentioned in Sections 2.2.2 and 2.2.3, XGB introduced trees to the ensembles one at a time and mitigates the prediction mistakes generated by the prior models, while Random Forest does not mitigate prediction mistakes. Therefore, the AUC scores for the XGB gradually increase and improve the performance of the algorithm. It should also be noted that despite having fewer trees as seen in the list on page 18, Random Forest using the data set with feature distance produces more nodes than XGB using the same data set because the size of each tree in the Random Forest is larger than the size of each tree in XGB.

6 Summary and Conclusions

This thesis analyzes the potential of data collected by AGV as an enabler of AI for telecommunication in industrial environments. The data in form of sensor data and wireless measurement from the AGV are utilized to predict LoS between the AGV and base station. The sensor data is analyzed to define the area of LoS and nLoS. Then, using data from the wireless measurement, several ML algorithms are used to give a prediction of LoS namely, Decision Tree, Random Forest, and XGB. The performance of each ML algorithm is compared by training two data sets. The first data set includes the features RSRP, RSRQ, RSSI, SINR, and distance while the second data set is constructed without the feature distance.

From analyzing the performance of each ML algorithm, the data set with the feature distance gives higher AUC scores than the data set without the feature distance and the feature distance plays a significant role in the prediction of LoS. However, the main reason distance is important, is because the area of LoS for this work only occurs when the AGV is at its closest to the base station. The algorithm took the distance values as a major decider to predict LoS since it is already clear that the closer the AGV is to the base station, the higher the probability of LoS. This could cause an issue when applied in other environments where LoS between AGV and the base station does not only occur when the AGV is at its closest.

The performance of the prediction model of each ML algorithm is ranked using the AUC score. In this case, the XGB algorithm outperforms other algorithms and the Random Forest performs slightly better than the Decision Tree. However, even when the AUC scores of Random Forest and Decision Tree are lower than XGB, each classification algorithm still gives a satisfactory performance with AUC scores of more than 0.92. At the end of this thesis, the performance of Random Forest and XGB as the number of nodes increases is also visualized to show how both algorithms work to achieve their final model. The results of this thesis could serve as a guideline for future measurements where LoS predictions are not as dependent on distance as in this work. For future applications, this thesis could be the early step to profile communication channels using AI. It could expand beyond the classification of LoS and nLoS by also considering other wireless measurement features.

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